

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LAWAL****FIRST NAME: BOLARINDE JOSEPH****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 01****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Aid for Generating Essay Topics and Steps of Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1– 4) and (Cleenerwerck, 2020)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 4-8, 24)
3. Some writing Rules of Thumb to Remember (EUCLID 2019, 14-23)
4. Use of Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56)
5. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)

UNDERSTANDING THE BASIC PRINCIPLES OF ACADEMIC WRITINGS

1) INTRODUCTION

This is the response paper (RP) from period one (1) of the course “International Academic Writing (Doctorate)”, the first course in the Euclid University’s Ph.D. Global Health and Health System (PHGH) degree. The International Academic Writing (Doctorate), coded ACA-401D has two study materials – a video by Prof Laurent Cleenerwerck (EUCLID 2020) as well as the ACA-401/ACA401D coursepack revised by Prof Laurent Cleenerwerck and Dr Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2019).

This response paper is therefore a tool to help assess my interaction and understanding of the study materials (EUCLID 2020, 3) for this course, and how the study would generally impact me. In this paper, the summary of the assigned study materials is highlighted.

The ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack is divided into nine chapters; each chapter is loaded with invaluable information and skills needed by scholars for writing meaningful

essays or scientific writings which meet up with today's English language and sustained readership. Chapters 1 to 3 aptly address the challenges that most beginners face – how to conceive and start essay writing and keep it flowing, understanding and avoiding plagiarism, and some important nuggets for writing papers (EUCLID 2019, 1– 16). Also, in these chapters, citation was defined as “Method used to indicate where a piece of information came from” (EUCLID 2019, 6).

Some basic details in writing, such as the use of punctuations, and when to use some common words are explicitly discussed in chapter four (EUCLID 2019, 17-22), while chapters 5 and 6 focus on styles of writing and the use of American or British English (EUCLID 2019, 24 -35).

Chapter 7 shows examples of corrections to a sample paper while chapters 8 and 9 elaborate on uses of American as against British English, and Latin abbreviations and expressions respectfully.

Professor Cleenewerck in the course video simplifies the use of rules and styles of writing in Microsoft word, highlighting the importance of heading styles as they are helpful in making the table of contents.

2) SECOND PART: REACTION TO THE BOOK

a) Aid for Generating Essay Topics and Steps of Writing

ACA-401/401D coursepack gave in-depth descriptions of the aim of essay writing and the **basic steps in writing an essay** (EUCLID 2019, 1 -4). This is a vital enlightenment for beginner researchers such as me. Many at times, we struggle with how to **conceive an idea to write on**, and how to put the thought into a professional piece. Understanding the aim of an academic essay is key, and the coursepack puts it as “to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1). As a professional working in a research institution, one of my major challenges with research was how to generate research topics, thankfully, the coursepack has demystified the process for me. This statement below is quite intuitive:

“A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers. Therefore, reading and researching are vital to essay writing. Researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question” (EUCLID 2019, 2).

This clue will be very handy for me as I take my doctoral degree journey with Euclid University. I believe that with the lessons learnt here plus guidance from the Faculty, I will generate my research thesis topic seamlessly.

Furthermore, both the coursepack and the video put a lot of importance on writing styles and the use of American or British English. Prof Cleenewerck in the course video explained how to use the ‘Styles’ function of the Microsoft Word software. He also taught

on the use of the software to include in-text references and reference list. This is of interest to me. I have authored a few publications either as first or co-author, but I have never understood these basic writing rules until now.

b) Plagiarism, its Implications, and How to Avoid it

Cleenewerck and Gulma in the ACA-401/410D coursepack explained the meaning, implication, and how to avoid **plagiarism** in academic writing. The material defined plagiarism as “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). Plagiarism which is a big offence that can attract academic penalty can be avoided by properly citing the author or the source from where the writer derived the information he or she is using (EUCLID 2019, 6). The document emphasised: “All academic essays **MUST** contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence” (EUCLID 2019, 4).

In addition, Cleenewerck and Gulma highlighted citation methods for in-text citations as well as list of work cited, referred to as ‘bibliography’ or ‘references’. They also explained in detail how and when to use quotations or paraphrases when citing. Based on the explanations in the study material, quotations “are the exact words of an author”. And “when you use a quotation, you must use quotation marks “.....” to capture what the author has said” (EUCLID 2019, 5-7). Paraphrasing on the other hand is the art of writing in one’s words and expressions the ideas and information derived from another author or source (EUCLID 2019, 8).

Moreover, the study material, ACA-401/410D coursepack provided various methods and styles of referencing other sources such as books, online works, journals, and so on. The Turabian citation style is highly recommended by the authors. To me, this is a new method, I have used the Vancouver and APA reference styles. The rule of thumb according to the authors is to ensure one is familiar with the school’s referencing specifications (EUCLID 2019, 24).

Based on what I have learnt from this course I have now understood why some papers are denied publications or recalled after they have been published. A doctoral student and earlier researchers must do their writings with this consciousness. This is an eye-opener for me to avoid plagiarism in my thesis and in any future publications.

c) Some writing Rules to Remember

The rules of thumb for writing as well as the important reminders discussed in the ACA-401/401D coursepack are very crucial (EUCLID 2019, 14-23). The points highlighted in these portions remind me of my first attempt to publish an article in a peer-reviewed journal. The article was rejected outrightly. My reflection on this coursework has helped me to realise where I got it wrong; some of these writing rules were violated. I have summarised some of the rules of thumb and important reminders prescribed by the study material below:

i) *Rule of Thumb for Writing*

The first **rule of thumb** is to state the main thesis at the beginning (or near) of the first paragraph. The Writing Centre of the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill describes thesis statement as a sentence of two, which provides a ‘road map’ for the reader to understand how the subject matter will be interpreted and what to expect from the paper (The Writing Center, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, 2020). Other rules of thumb provided in the ACA-401/401D coursepack include writing clearly, support assertion, among others. The need to avoid plagiarism was reiterated in this portion as well (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)

ii) *Important Reminders in Writing*

Chapter Four of the ACA-401/401D Coursepack enumerated eleven points to remember when writing. The points hinge on appropriate use of comma, punctuation, apostrophe, and pronouns. It also emphasises the need to make subject and verb agree with each other, and to omit unnecessary words. Besides, when a number should be written out in words, or written in numerals are explored (EUCLID 2019, 17 - 23). These are highly important reminders that are often overlooked in writing. However, I would love to see Chapter 4 titled differently as the current title “Literature Review” seems inappropriate.

d) *Use of Latin Abbreviations and Expressions in English Writing*

Another exciting exposition contained in the ACA-401/401D coursepack is the lessons on the **use of Latin abbreviations and expressions** in writing. This portion shows the Latin abbreviations and expressions and their English equivalents. The authors guided that “Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing (e.g., the information in parentheses)”, but also cautioned that “in business, formal, and technical writing, use the English equivalent of the abbreviation to avoid misinterpretation by your readers” (EUCLID 2019, 56). In personal and academic writings, I had previously used some of the Latin abbreviations with wrong meanings. As this doctoral degree will involve several writings, learning about these words is going to be extremely helpful to me.

e) *American Versus British English*

The use of **American against British English** is a highly significant point discussed in the ACA-401/401D. The authors keenly elaborate on some of the differences between the two forms of English language. Some of the differences include words having different pronunciations but the same spellings, different spellings but the same pronunciations, same words but different or additional meanings, and so on. Based on several highlighted parameters, American English has been adjudged as the currently most widely used English globally (EUCLID 2019, 27-35) and (Goncalves et al. 2018).

As an aspiring Global Health and Health Systems expert, I will be expected to do lots of writings, for example, grant proposals, research proposals, project reports, publications, among other things, it is of high importance for me to understand the use of the American or British English as my writings will be targeting varying groups. I am excited to be getting these skills at this very beginning, and I believe that as I write my response papers and major papers I will be developed further.

3) CONCLUSION

As a newly enrolled doctoral student at Euclid University, I did not know what to expect concerning writing academic papers. This is an area I dreaded so much but going through the study video and ACA-401/401D coursepack, my fears have been allayed and confidence built in me. From studying these materials and watching the video I am amazed to see how attention is paid to details; this gladdens my heart and I am convinced that I have made the best choice of institution to obtain my doctoral degree.

REFERENCES

- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.
- Cleenewerck Laurent. 2020. Basic ACA-401 Tutorial. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed on 14 September 2020)
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2020. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.
- Euclid University. 2020. *Student Orientation – Print and Keep on Hand*. Bangui Central African Republic: Euclid University
- Goncalves, Bruno, Lucia Loureiro-Porto, Jose J. Ramasco, and David Sanchez. 2018. "Mapping the Americanization of English in Space and Time." *PLOS ONE* 13 (5).
- The Writing Center, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. n.d. "Thesis Statements." Accessed September 12, 2020. <https://writingcenter.unc.edu/tips-and-tools/thesis-statements/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.